

Sudoku: molecules and reactions

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Abstract—Chemical computation model was inspired by chemical reactions: procedures react with data as molecules of compounded solutions react to each other. This model has a concurrent and non-deterministic way of computing, that results transparent parallelism instead of artificially sequential algorithms. There has been some theoretical examination of this model, but there are not many practical usage. In this paper chemical approach is used to solve a well-known logical game, Sudoku. The basics of Higher-Order Chemical Language and the chemical computation model is explained through the case-study of solving sudoku puzzle.

Keywords—parallel computing, multiset rewriting, Higher-Order Chemical Language, sudoku-solving

I. INTRODUCTION

Computational tasks are usually modelled as sequence of atomic steps, but this is not the only way to represent them. Very often both the "step" and the "sequence" is artificially created abstraction for the task, that is derived from the computing architecture instead of the computation task itself[1].

Computation can be represented as reactions of molecules[2]: a solution contains data and procedures, which reacts according to given reaction rules. So that, the computation is realized through reactions, that occurs parallel and in random order. In this abstraction it is not possible to determine which molecules would react to each other "next", only if they are able to react. Moreover, the concept of "next reaction" is not exist in this paradigm either. From the basis of this model there are no order of computation, only random and parallel reactions[3][4].

Chemical model was already suggested for some fields of application, such as workflow scheduling in heterogen, distributed environment[5], or autonomous mailing system[6], but until the recent years there were no tools to examine these in practice. A few years ago an interpreter was created to execute chemical applications.

This approach is far from the von Neumann computation model, where instructions are executed in (almost) exactly that order, they are written.

In section II. γ -calculus, the formalism of the chemical computation model is described. In section III. Higher-order Chemical Language, a declarative programming language based on γ -calculus is introduced, in section IV complexity of sudoku solving problem is summarized, in section V. usual sudoku solving techniques are described as a comparison for the chemical solving method, and the HOCL solution is

presented in section VI and in section VII a chemical solver based on optimization problem is discussed.

II. CHEMICAL CALCULUS

As the λ -calculus for functional paradigm, the γ -calculus means the mathematical background of the chemical computing paradigm. The basic data structure of γ -calculus is the multiset, that represents the chemical solution, and contains active and passive molecules[7], [3].

The γ -abstraction is an active molecule, that represents the procedure and its role is similar to λ -abstraction. Molecules can be involved in a reaction are chosen by pattern-matching in a single atomic step and these molecules can be either passive or active molecules as well, because of the higher-order nature of the model[7], [3].

Then reductions are performed according to the reaction rules, where expressions are replaced by abstraction body. Graphically, reaction consumes molecules and might create others instead. This can be written formally in *gamma*, equation (1) [3].

$$\gamma \langle x \rangle .M, \langle N \rangle \rightarrow M[x := N] \quad (1)$$

γ -expressions are associative and commutative, so they can be reeducated in arbitrary order. These properties ensure the concept of the Brownian motion, the constant and random motion of molecules in liquids and gases [8].

If a solution contains an active, reactive molecule, that can react other molecules, the solution is also called active, and the solution is active until it contains any reactive molecules. When the solution contains no more reactive molecules become inert and its content is the result of the computation[3]. By adding newer molecules to the solution, it can be reactivated and continue the computation.

Where as λ -expressions can be represented in a tree structure, the γ -expressions do not have predefined structure in a solution, their position is continually changing accordingly to the Brownian motion [8], [3].

III. HIGHER-ORDER CHEMICAL LANGUAGE

Higher-Order Chemical Language is a programming language based on γ -calculus (another is [9]), and its most important role is to ensure a well-usable and readable syntactical tool-set. HOCL contains one instruction to do this: **replace P by M if C in $\langle \rangle$** , where P is the pattern what to be replaced to M, C is the condition when to replace, and between angle

brackets the molecules of the solution are listed where the reactions occur.

A passive molecule can be a value, a pair or a solution. Although a solution can contains any number of molecules (and they do not have order), a pair contains exactly two molecules with a defined order.

The model does not define exactly what kind of values can be stored in a molecule, so the interpreter [4] uses basic types of the language in which is written.

The usual way to get factorial of a number is using a loop to compute products in a specified order [10], the chemical way is using an active molecule that replaces two molecules to another that contains the product of their values (2).

$$prod = \mathbf{replace} X, Y \mathbf{by} X * Y \quad (2)$$

And adding (passive) molecules to a solution, each of them contains a value from 2 to N (when calculating $N!$). The algorithm is terminating when only one number left, and that contains $N!$.

IV. COMPLEXITY OF SUDOKU

Sudoku, in the most popular form, is a 9×9 matrix, that divided to nine 3×3 submatrices, where some cell are filled with numbers from 1 to 9, others are blank. The task is to fill every blank cell in such a way that every row, column, and submatrix contains a number only once.

A 9×9 matrix using sudoku rules can be filled in about $6,67 \times 10^{21}$ ways [11], the prefilled numbers constrains this to exactly one. There has to be at least 17 given numbers (clues) to an exact solution [12].

Solving a generalized, N order sudoku, which is an $N^2 \times N^2$ matrix divided to $N^2 \times N^2$ submatrices is an NP-complete problem[13].

Sudoku belongs to a more general problem class, the constraint satisfaction problem, that can be solved with constraint propagation [14]. Constraint propagation uses reasoning to determine cell values, not guaranteed to solve the puzzle, but it is the natural way how human players solve sudoku [14].

There are numerous different solving technique[15], that are usually ranked by difficulty. This ranking (scores) and the variety of these techniques required to use to solve the sudoku is often used for rating sudoku puzzles by difficulty[16], [14].

Gaby Vanhegan introduced [17] a similar approach, but instead of creating a summarized score, a five level "code" is created such as 1.4.2 which means one level 1 technique, four level 2 techniques and two level 3 techniques is necessary to solve the puzzle.

Ercsey-Ravasz and Toroczkai introduced[18] a logarithmic, "Richter"-type scale for sudoku hardness, (TABLE I) shows its classes, where no puzzles $\eta > 4$ [18].

TABLE I: Sudoku difficulty classes by Ercsey-Ravasz – Toroczkai

difficulty	score
easy	$0 < \eta \leq 1$
medium	$1 < \eta \leq 2$
hard	$2 < \eta \leq 3$
ultra hard	$3 < \eta \leq 4$

In 2007, Arto Inkala published in his book a sudoku puzzle, called Ai Escargot (Fig. 1) and he claimed that it is the most difficult sudoku puzzle[19].

1				7		9		
	3			2				8
		9	6			5		
		5	3			9		
	1			8				2
6					4			
3							1	
	4							7
		7				3		

Fig. 1: AI Escargot[19]

V. SUDOKU SOLVING TECHNIQUES

Every sudoku can be solved by brute force technique[16], but only those are surveyed in this paper, that can be solved with logical reasoning. First, a human player can also solve these puzzles and second, the chemical model has a forward chaining production system like execution. Also, guessing and backtracking solving methods are not surveyed either.

As the chemical computing paradigm has similarities with functional programming and rule based production systems, so sudoku solvers mainly in these paradigms are used as reference for implementation, and one of the most important is a sample code of Drools open source production system, because of its rule-based approach, that uses some more advanced solving techniques as well.

It is worth to mention that chemical approach is not the only nature inspired method that used to solve sudoku puzzles, for example Artificial Bee Colony[?] (optimization) algorithm is also used to solve this problem[20].

VI. SOLUTION IN HOCL

Sudoku is a matrix, which elements are ordered, and this order contains information. But order in HOCL data structure (solution) is not defined, that makes it difficult to represent this information in the chemical language. A reaction is necessary to modify the value of a cell and the molecule, that is represent this cell, must be participated in the reaction. Moreover, its context (cells in its row, column and submatrix) must also participate in the reaction to determine the which number can be write into the cell. This would mean 21 cells must be participate at every "write operation". A molecule can be participated in only one reaction at the same time which

Fig. 2: Sudoku cell represented as relation database

means parallel solving is not possible in this way, because two different cell cannot be chosen with its context without collusion.

Therefore, a different approach is needed, the used one is similar to how normalized relational database schemas are designed. Administrative solutions used to store information about the 'state' of every row, column and submatrix (hereafter simply group). This information should be able to tell which numbers are already in that group.

At this point let us take that there is a calculated value, that tells exactly which numbers are in a certain group, this problem will be detailed later in this section. Figure 2 shows a simple schema with four tables, where every cell has an identification number (cell), a value and three foreign key attribute to the group tables primary keys.

Figure 4 show the chemical data structure of a cell with a similar schema. A circle is molecule with some content. A molecule can be a solution and pair as well, so outer circles represent solutions, circles connected with two lines are pairs. A cell is a solution with five pairs: cell id, value, row, column and submatrix ids, those are "foreign keys". It is important to note that this does not mean any model or language level connection, they are merely referenced in program logic. The group solutions contain two pairs with an id and a value, that represents the of content the group. With this representation when an empty cell is chosen (randomly) it can be determined which value can be written into it, using the information stored in the group solutions.

In a correctly filled sudoku each group could be a set, since every number can occur only once in a group, but a solution is a multiset, so multiple occurrence of an element is possible. If it was a set and trying to push a number again triggered an exception then it would be easy to detect some false positioning of a number. Explicit detection rules are necessary, but available tools are limited for this task, hence it is not specified exactly what kind of constants can be used in a molecule [10]. So at the developing of the HOCL interpreter (used in this paper) simply Java types were used [4].

First idea was to use flag fields (such as unix-like permissions) for each groups. For ten values a four-bit flag field is necessary and for the evaluation bitwise XOR operator in the language level, however usable operators in HOCL are not specified. At the interpreter layer all operators are usable that are provided by the Jess production system, which used for constructing the interpreter. In Jess there is only bitwise AND, OR and NOT operators, although XOR would be constructable

Fig. 3: Molecule structure representing a cell and group values

from these operators for a nine-input XOR it is not practical.

Second thought was to use algebra of sets. If a (randomly) chosen number is in the relevant row, column or submatrix than this number cannot be written into the chosen cell. Although solutions are multisets, set operations are not defined in this model, so it is not possible to get the union, intersection or complementation of solutions.

Third idea was to use the content of the cell for solving the sudoku, so use more than just a state of the cell, hence it is not even necessary to use numbers in sudoku, letters or any other stave can be used instead of numbers. The only role of numbers to differentiate the ten state of a cell (empty and numbers from 1 to 9) and using numbers is easy and widely understandable for human solvers.

So, numbers from 1 to 9 are replaced to prime numbers from 2 to 23 and the empty cell is marked by 1. Group content values are calculated as product of the (prime) numbers of the corresponding cells. As the product consists of prime numbers, every combination of a group content results a unique value. In this case the modulo operation can simply determine if a number is in a group, because the result is zero.

The next problem was that an 'intersection-like' operation is still required, but greatest common divisor of the group products can be used for this task. As there is no closed form of greatest common divisor and it cannot be implemented as a function, hence functions are not defined in chemical model a generic approach cannot be used. But in this approach there are only a finite number of prime numbers.

Let ρ, κ, σ be the values of row, column and the submatrix and let $\zeta = \rho * \kappa * \sigma$. Then with the expression 3 it is possible to determine the greatest common divisor of the prime number products.

$$\sum_{r \in [2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23]} 0^{\zeta \bmod r^3} * r \quad (3)$$

When the greatest common divisor is prime (so a single number) the $\sum_{r \in [2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23]} 0^{\zeta \bmod r^3}$ expression results one, otherwise zero. The r multiplier achieve that the whole expression results the greatest common divisor itself in

Fig. 4: Expanded molecule structure of a cell

these circumstances and can be used in the IF-THEN statement of an active molecule.

VII. SUDOKU AS AN OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

In the previous section the preparations of solving sudoku as a constraint satisfaction problem was discussed, but it can also be considered as an optimization problem.

To do this the figure 4 data structure is used with some modification: a new pair added to store whether this cell is fixed or not. A cell is “fixed” if it is part of puzzle and “not fixed” if it stores a computed value.

This structure with the administrative group molecules seems the most perfect data structure for solving sudoku regardless of the exact solving method. Besides the “fixed pair”, additional enhancements are necessary: let cell values be represented as numbers from 0 to 9 (0 is the empty cell), and the calculation of group values have to be modified according to expression 4, where γ is the group. Then summary every group gives the total error value. The optimal, solved value is zero, hence when the sudoku is correctly solved the sum of every row, column and submatrix is 45, so the distance from 45 is 0.

$$|45 - \sum_{r=1}^9 \gamma_r| \quad (4)$$

This solving method is based on [21], that uses simulated annealing to solve the optimization problem. In the first step every missing numbers are written into empty cells randomly. Then random replacements occur that intends to reduce the total error. This replacing method fits well to the chemical model, because the only operator is the **replace** operator.

At some point no more replacement might able to happen, this can be local minimum. Simulated annealing uses ‘reheat’ when the process stick in a local optimum. In chemical model the algorithm terminates when no more reaction can occur, but the solution can reactive at any time by adding molecules. The example of 2, if newer numbers are added the computation will continue with the pre-existed active molecule. But new active molecule can be also added. When local optimum reached, a new active molecule can be add, that randomly reverses some cell values then inactivate itself and the regular solving algorithm can continue its work.

Naturally no replacement can affect to the key cells, it is the reason why fixed property is introduced.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper the design objectives of a sudoku solver were presented in an unconventional, nature inspired computing paradigm and the relying programming language. The suitable chemical data-structure is presented to solve the sudoku puzzle.

This real world task focused on some deficiency of the interpreter and gave many experience in writing algorithms in HOCL. The future work to improve the interpreter and the solving HOCL algorithms, the ‘constraint satisfaction’ solver now can solve some really simple sudoku, but cannot handle the most ones. The ‘optimization’ solver has the advantage, because it should solve every sudoku.

The drawback of this prime code method is that the product of the first nine prime number is relatively big (223092870) and the product of three number of this order does not fit into a 32-bit integer. And this is just the most well-known 9x9 sudoku, with solving bigger ones this problem just escalates.

Using binary flag fields and XOR-ing would result much easier and faster execution of chemical algorithms, so implementing this operator is one important direction of development of the interpreter. This task is not even too complicated, hence bitwise XOR operator exists in Java and it is easy to implement a user function into Jess, which is the base of intermediate language used in the interpreter.

DISCLAIMER

The manuscript was written as a student scientific project supervised by Zsolt Németh during my MSc studies in 2014. The text left as I wrote back then with all its faults, but still wanted to make available for archiving reasons. As the affiliations are not accurate anymore no e-mail address provided, but my contact address is available via my ORCID.

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